

COMPARISON OF SCR MICROWAVE MEASUREMENT OF DIRECTIONAL WAVE SPECTRA WITH ARSLOE IN-SITU SENSOR

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ABSTRACT

A 36 GHz computer-controlled airborne radar is described which generates a false-color coded elevation map of the sea surface below the aircraft in real-time and can routinely produce ocean directional wave spectra with off-line data processing. Data products are shown and the procedures for correcting the encounter spectra for platform effects are indicated. The non-directional frequency spectrum and Fourier coefficients computed from the radar spectrum were in good agreement with those computed from the NOAA XERB buoy.

INTRODUCTION

The Surface Contour Radar (SCR) was developed jointly by NASA Wallops Flight Center (WFC) and the Naval Research Laboratory under the NASA Advanced Applications Flight Experiments program. It is an airborne computer-controlled 36-GHz bistatic radar which produces a real-time topographical map of the surface beneath the aircraft. The SCR is one of the most straightforward remote sensing instruments in measurement concept. It provides great ease of data interpretation since it involves a direct range measurement.

The system (Kenney, *et al.*, 1979) was designed to measure the directional wave spectra of the ocean surface. Figure 1 shows the nominal measurement geometry and the horizontal resolutions in terms of the aircraft altitude, h . An oscillating mirror scans a $0.85^\circ \times 1.2^\circ$ pencil-beam laterally to measure the elevations at 51 evenly spaced points on the surface below the aircraft within a swath which is approximately half the aircraft altitude. At each of the points the SCR measures the slant range to the surface and corrects in real-time for the off-nadir angle of the beam to produce the elevation of the point in question with respect to the horizontal reference.

The elevations are false-color coded and displayed on the SCR color TV monitor so that real-time estimates of significant wave height (SWH), dominant wavelength, and direction of propagation can be made. The real-time display allows the aircraft altitude and flight lines to be optimized during the flight even if there was not a prior knowledge of the wave conditions.

AIRCRAFT VERTICAL MOTION REMOVAL

The aircraft generally has some altitude variation during the time interval in which the data are acquired that contaminates the elevation measurements. The aircraft motion is eliminated by doubly-integrating the output of a vertical motion sensing accelerometer to obtain an independent estimate of the aircraft motion. To compensate for any uncertainties in the initial values of the aircraft altitude, vertical velocity, and the accelerometer constant, a parabola of the form $a_0 + a_1y + a_2y^2$ must also be least-squares fitted over the data span and subtracted from the elevation data. The variable y is the along-track distance. The resulting elevation data may still contain some small residual aircraft motion but it is much lower in amplitude and frequency than the wave data.

DATA ANALYSIS

Figure 2 shows sets of 1024 scan lines of SCR elevation data taken during the Atlantic Remote Sensing Land Ocean Experiment (ARSLOE) within minutes of each other. The sets have been oriented in the proper round track directions. The data were taken at 400 m altitude along the three different aircraft ground tracks. The troughs are dark and the crests are light so that the data have the visual appearance of waves illuminated by a low sun angle. Distance along the ground track increases by approximately 5 m per line. The cross track spacing of the 51 elevation points is the altitude divided by 100, or roughly 4 m. The data point spacing in the TV monitor elevation display is approximately the same both along track and cross track. Therefore, there is a geometric distortion in the display whenever the actual along track and cross track data point spacings are not equal. The geometric distortion in Figure 2 is small and caused principally by the variation of the aircraft ground speed on the various ground tracks.

The directional wave spectra are produced by performing two-dimensional FFTs on the sets of 1,024 scan lines. The along-track dimension of approximately 5 km produces an along track spectral resolution of $(2\pi)/5000 \text{ m}^{-1}$ in wave number space, whereas the cross-track resolution is only $2\pi/200 \text{ m}^{-1}$ so the grid of FFT points is badly out of proportion.

For the final display on the color TV monitor, the spectrum is oriented with respect to true North and FFT data points are filled-in cross-track so the display is in proper proportion.

Figure 3 shows the results of averaging four spectra taken during the ARSLOE experiment on a 314° ground track at 215 m altitude. It is a black and white presentation of the false-color coded variance spectrum whose ten color levels change at the 1, 4, 9, 16, 25, 36, 49, 64 and 81 percent levels of the spectral maximum. The ground track is indicated by the white radial from the origin. The banding that is apparent in Figure 3 parallel to the aircraft ground track is the effect of the poor lateral spectral resolution. Even so, the spectrum is still very well defined.

Figure 4 shows a black and white presentation of false-color coded data taken in the North Atlantic from an altitude of 800 m when the SWH was approximately 5 m and the dominant wavelength was 200 m. By varying the aircraft altitude the spatial resolution and swath width can be adjusted as dictated by the sea state.

CORRECTIONS FOR AIRCRAFT GROUND SPEED AND DRIFT ANGLE

Figure 5 shows the average of four variance spectra for each of two different flight directions at 400 m altitude for the same day as the elevation shown in Figure 2. The SWH was predominantly swell arriving from the northeast. The color levels change at the 1, 4, 9, 16, 25, 36, 49, 64 and 81 percent levels of the spectral maximum. The agreement between the two flight directions is excellent. The reference direction in the k plane is the direction towards which the waves are traveling, not from which they are coming. The actual spectra in Figure 5 are in the lower half plane. The 180°-ambiguity image in the upper half plane is an artifact of the FFT process since the elevation data could represent waves traveling in either direction.

If one examines the spectra carefully it is apparent that the encounter spectrum and its 180°-ambiguity image are more widely separated for the northeast ground track than for the southeast. Also the radial joining the spectral peaks is rotated clockwise in the southeast ground track spectrum relative to the northeast ground track. These changes are caused by the aircraft velocity and drift angle and must be corrected to obtain the actual spectrum from the encounter spectrum.

Since it took approximately 50 seconds to acquire each of the 1024 scan line sets shown in Figure 2, the data does not represent an instantaneous elevation map of the surface. The waves at the end of the segment would have moved by several wavelengths relative to the positions they were in when the data at the beginning of the segment was recorded. If the waves were traveling in the same direction as the aircraft their wavelength would appear longer. If they were traveling in the opposite direction as the aircraft their apparent wavelength would appear shorter. For waves traveling

at an angle to the aircraft ground track there would be changes in both the apparent wavelength and the direction of propagation.

The drift angle is the amount by which the aircraft heading differs from the aircraft ground track. If the aircraft is following its nose the drift angle is zero. If the aircraft heading is to the left of the ground track to compensate for the cross-track component of the wind velocity. The aircraft ground track then drifts to the right relative to its heading. For no drift angle, all the points in the k plane migrate anti-parallel to the aircraft ground track and the magnitude of the change is proportional to the magnitude of the original k-vector (Long, 1979). When the drift angle is non-zero there is also a cross track component to the displacement in the k plane.

Corresponding to the two spectra of Figure 5, Figure 6 shows overlays of the plots of the variance spectra before (top) and after (bottom) applying the corrections just discussed. In applying the corrections, no a priori knowledge of the direction of propagation was assumed. In effect, all the data were assumed to be real and corrected accordingly. It can be seen that the corrections have caused the two reference lines to coalesce in the actual spectrum of the lower right, while they are spread further apart in the 180°-ambiguity spectrum in the upper left. The corrections compensate the correct spectrum but are in the wrong direction for the other one and worsen the disparity between the flight directions. Rejection of the ambiguous lobe can be accomplished by examining the absolute magnitude of the differences at the crossing points on the spectral lobes for perpendicular flight lines.

SPECTRAL COMPARISON WITH PITCH AND ROLL BUOY

Figure 7 shows the approximate ground tracks for the SCR during data acquisition on November 12, 1980 (Figures 2, 5, and 8). Also shown are the shoreline, the Field Research Facility pier of the Coastal Engineering Research Center, and the XERB pitch-and-roll buoy which was directly offshore at a distance of approximately 35 km. The SCR flight lines occurred half way between two observations by the XERB which were spaced at six hour intervals. The figure indicates the wave heights and wind speeds observed by the buoy and the wave height indicated by the SCR. The local wind had been from the North-northwest all day but the dominant waves on the surface were swell coming from the northeast. The wind changed little over the six hour period surrounding the SCR data.

In an earlier comparison of these data sets (Walsh *et al.*, 1981) the average of the two buoy spectra was compared with the SCR spectrum. The main disparity between the spectra was that the SCR spectrum half-power width at the spectral peak was 40° whereas the pitch-and-roll buoy indicated a width of 160°. This was not surprising since pitch-and-roll buoys have the ability to measure only five Fourier coefficients. Truncating the Fourier series at the second harmonic results in

negative side lobes for the directional spectrum and poor directional resolution. Longuet-Higgins et al. (1963) used a non-negative smoothing function to weight the Fourier series coefficients to remove the negative side lobes and a similar smoothing function had been applied to the XERB data (Kenneth Steele, private communication). The directional resolution obtained by the buoy would be expected to be poor because the effective width of this smoothed directional spectrum (width of a rectangle of height equal to peak energy density and area equal to that of the main lobe) is 135° , while the highest resolution attainable with two harmonics without smoothing is 72° (Panicker, 1974). This means that the buoy spectra could have been narrowed if the appearance of negative side lobes had been tolerated. But the spectral width would never approach 40° , which demonstrated the significantly higher resolution of the SCR compared with pitch-and-roll buoys.

It was later discovered (Lau et al., 1982) that C_{33} had been omitted in the a_2 Fourier coefficient computed by the buoy (Longuet-Higgins et al., 1963). Therefore the buoy spectrum used for the previous comparison was in error by an unknown amount. The buoy problem has been corrected but the a_2 coefficient in the historical data has been irretrievably lost (Kenneth Steele, private communication).

In this paper we shall compare the non-directional spectrum and the three correct Fourier coefficients computed by the buoy with those computed from the SCR. Figures 8 and 9 deal with SCR data from a single 1024 scan line data set taken from 400 m altitude on a 238° ground track at ($36.2^\circ, -74.4^\circ$). A linear interpolation was made in the k-plane to increase the cross track density of points by a factor of four. Each of the points was then corrected for the effects of aircraft ground speed and drift angle discussed earlier and then transformed into the appropriate interval in the frequency plane.

The top of Figure 8 compares the non-dimensional XERB buoy spectra three hours before and after the SCR flight. The wave height reduced over the interval and the disappearance of the peak at 0.13 Hertz indicated that the swell coming from the northeast had diminished. The bottom of Figure 8 compares the SCR directional spectrum with the buoy spectrum taken three hours after the flight. The agreement is quite good considering the change in the buoy spectra over the period. Also shown is the SCR spectrum after correction for the spatial filtering effect of the radar footprint. The correction becomes significant above 0.20 Hertz and pulls the SCR spectrum well above the buoy spectrum in that region. This is probably caused by noise in the radar elevation measurements and procedures for eliminating it are being developed.

Figure 9 compares the Fourier coefficients in the form used by Hasselmann et al. (1980). The magnitudes of the XERB buoy Fourier coefficients were generally larger than unity for 0.05 Hertz or below and were not plotted. Kenneth Steele (private communication) suggested that the error could have

been caused by an imperfect vendor calibration on the heave sensor at low frequencies. The agreement between the two systems is once again quite good.

CONCLUSIONS

The SCR provides a high resolution way to easily and directly measure sea surface directional wave spectra. It will be extremely useful in developing oceanographic models as well as validating indirect remote sensing oceanographic techniques such as side-looking radars and wave spectrometers.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The XERB buoy data were provided by Kenneth Steele of the NOAA Data Buoy Office and he is thanked for discussions concerning the buoy. Gary L. Donner of Gary Donner Associates developed the real-time software for the radar system as well as the software for the wave spectrum and elevation displays. Robert Swift of EG&G Washington Analytical Services Center, Inc., helped develop the off-line data analysis programs and supervises the routine reduction and archiving of SCR data.

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Figure 1. SCR measurement geometry and horizontal resolutions.

Figure 2. Three sets of 1024 scan lines of grey-scale elevation data which were acquired on 11/12/80 at 400 m altitude. North is vertical and the data have been oriented in the respective aircraft ground track directions.

LAT N	36.20.5	ALT	215±	2	DATE	23 OCT 80
LON W	75.31.3	RES	1.0		TIME	22.14.3.4
GTK	313.9±.4	GS	104±	2	FILE	339
DA	-6.8±.5	L/S	19.5±.97		RCRD	30/1024
ROL	1.3±1.1	CI	16		DATA E ONLY	1/0

Figure 3. Black and white presentation of false-color coded variance spectrum for the average of four spectra at 215 m altitude. The color changes at the 1, 4, 9, 16, 25, 36, 49, 64 and 81 percent levels relative to the spectral peak.

Figure 4. Black and white presentation of false-color coded 800 m altitude elevation data and variance spectrum for a day with 5 m SWH and 200 m dominant wavelength.

Figure 5. Black and white presentations of false-color coded averages of four variance spectra for the aircraft ground tracks indicated by the white radial in the displays.

Figure 6. Overlay in the k plane of the variance spectra of Figure 5 before (top) and after (bottom) the corrections for the aircraft ground speed and drift angle are applied. The radials extend from the origin and indicate the direction of North.

Figure 7. SCR ground tracks and XERB pitch-and-roll buoy location for 11/12/80.

Figure 8. Comparison of non-directional spectra from SCR and XERB buoy. The dotted curve in the bottom plot indicates the SCR data after correction for the spatial filtering effect of the radar footprint.

Figure 9. Comparison of Fourier coefficients from SCR and XERB buoy.